

Efficacy of Isobaric Levobupivacaine and Hyperbaric Bupivacaine under Spinal Anaesthesia in the Lower Limb Surgeries

G. Uday Kumar¹, Koti Sreenivasa Rao²

¹Associate Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, Mamatha Medical College, Khammam, Telangana, India.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Anesthesia, MNR Medical College and Hospital, Sangareddy, Telangana, India.

Received: 26-10-2022 / Revised: 30-11-2022 / Accepted: 28-12-2022

Corresponding author: Dr Koti Sreenivasa Rao

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Introduction: Spinal anaesthesia is more desirable choice for lower limb orthopedic procedures. Bupivacaine is a drug of choice for spinal anaesthesia and isobaric levobupivacaine is an enantiomer of bupivacaine has low central nervous system and cardiotoxic effect. The present was designed to assess the efficacy of isobaric levobupivacaine and hyperbaric bupivacaine in the elective lower limb surgeries under spinal anaesthesia.

Materials and methods: Forty-eight cases between 21 to 50 years of age undergoing elective lower limb surgery belong to ASA grade I and II were considered. Participants were randomly divided in to group A (3 ml 0.5% intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine) and group B (3 ml 0.5% intrathecal hyperbaric bupivacaine). Details of sensory and motor blockade, hemodynamic parameters and details of postoperative adverse events were recorded.

Results: The total duration of sensory block was 181.95±2.89 and 209.36±4.58 and the total duration of motor block was 205.34±5.56 and 213.98±6.34 in groups A & B respectively. Hypotension was seen in 29.16% and 8.33%, bradycardia in 16.66% and 4.16% and nausea/vomiting in 20.83% and 8.33% of cases in hyperbaric bupivacaine and isobaric levobupivacaine groups respectively.

Conclusion: The intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine have shown less duration, slow onset of sensory & motor blockade, stable hemodynamic parameters and incidence of hypotension, bradycardia and nausea/vomiting was less than intrathecal hyperbaric bupivacaine.

Keywords: Hyperbaric Bupivacaine, Isobaric Levobupivacaine, Orthopedic Surgery, Sensory Blockade, Motor Blockade.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Regional anaesthesia is commonly used choice for the lower limb orthopedic surgeries especially spinal anaesthesia [1]. Spinal anaesthesia is rapid in onset, facilitates effective sensory and motor blockade and has less thromboembolic episodes. Bupivacaine

is the common drug of choice for spinal anaesthesia, with unpleasant effects including hypotension, bradycardia, longer duration of motor blockade, cardiotoxicity and central nervous system toxicity [2,3].

Levobupivacaine is the S-enantiomer of racemic bupivacaine and has less of negative inotropism and decreased affinity for cardiac sodium channels than bupivacaine. Levobupivacaine is equal to bupivacaine in terms of safety and efficacy [4,5]. The extent of isobaric solution in cerebrospinal fluid does not relate on patient position during and after the injection. Therefore, intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine does not extent unexpectedly high and levels of sensory block is not affected by alteration of position of patient after injection [6].

Hyperbaric local anaesthetics are gaining importance in the spinal anaesthesia due to their effective sensory and motor block than bupivacaine, ropivacaine and levobupivacaine alone [7,8]. Hyperbaric bupivacaine is considered as gold standard choice for spinal anaesthesia in India. However, hyperbaric solutions may lead to sudden cardiac arrest after spinal anaesthesia due to extension of the sympathetic block [9,10].

There is scarcity in the literature on efficacy of intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine and intrathecal hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb orthopaedic surgeries, this study was designed to assess the details of sensory and motor blockade, hemodynamic changes and related complication with the intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine and intrathecal hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb orthopaedic surgeries

Materials and Methods

The present prospective randomized study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesiology in association with department of Orthopedics at MNR Medical College and Hospital, Sangareddy during January 2021 to August 2022. Forty-eight cases between 21 to 50 years of age undergoing elective lower limb surgery were considered. Cases belong to ASA grade I and

II, undergoing elective lower limb surgery were included. Cases with history of lower limb joint surgeries, skeletal deformity, Neurological and cerebrovascular disorders, coagulopathy, contradict to study drugs and not willing to participate were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from study participants and study protocol was approved by institutional ethics committee.

Study Participants were randomly allotted to two study groups i.e., group A administered with intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine 0.5% (3 ml) and group B administered with intrathecal hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5% (3 ml). All participants were undergone pre anesthetic evaluation including complete physical examination, necessary laboratory investigations, and ECG.

Before procedure, baseline values of blood pressure, heart rate and SPO₂ was recorded. Patients were advised to lie in lateral position, under aseptic conditions lumbar puncture was done at the level of L3/L4 in midline. The study drugs were administered into subarachnoid space using 25G spinal needle and place patient in supine position.

Parameters like time of onset of sensory block, time to peak sensory block and duration of sensory block was measured by pin prick test at 2 min, 4 min, 6 min, 8 min, 10 min, 12 min, and 15 min after drug injection. Duration of complete motor block and duration of motor block was evaluated by modified Bromage score. In addition, hemodynamic parameters including heart rate, pulse rate, systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), SPO₂ and respiratory rate were assessed.

The collected data was analyzed by SPSS 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to analyse demographic data. Chi-square test and unpaired student 't' test was used to compare the group. P<0.05 was considered statistically significant outcome.

Results

Table 1: Demographic data of study participants.

Demographic data	Group A (n=24)	Group B (n=24)
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Age (In years)		
21-30	05 (20.84%)	05 (20.84%)
31-40	11 (45.83%)	13 (54.16%)
41-50	08 (33.33%)	06 (25%)
Gender		
Male	13 (54.16%)	12 (50%)
Female	11 (45.83%)	12 (50%)
Weight (In Kgs)	53.21±7.68	54.02±9.55
Height (In cm)	154.2±6.39	156.12±8.86
BMI Kg/m ²	23.56±3.82	24.28±4.04
ASA Grade		
Grade I	13 (54.16%)	15 (62.5%)
Grade II	11 (45.83%)	09 (37.5%)

Table 2: Comparison of sensory and motor block between study groups

Sensory block	Group A	Group B	p-value
	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	
Sensory block			
Duration to onset	7.84±5.36	5.54±4.94	0.0274
Duration to peak	11.03±0.98	7.82±0.86	0.001
Total duration of sensory block	181.95±2.89	209.36±4.58	0.0305
Motor block			
Duration of complete motor block	8.81±1.12	6.42±1.78	0.001
Total duration of motor block	205.34±5.56	213.98±6.34	0.001
Duration of analgesia	130.48±4.83	151.14±6.52	0.0183

Graph 1: Mean systolic blood pressure between two study groups

Graph 2: Mean diastolic blood pressure between two study groups

Graph 3: Comparison of mean Pulse rate among two study groups

Graph 4: Comparison of mean arterial pressure among two study groups

Graph 5: Comparison of mean SPO2 among two study groups

Table 3: Post-operative adverse events among two study groups

Adverse events	Group A	Group B	p-value
	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	
Nausea/vomiting	2 (8.33%)	5 (20.83%)	0.0254
Hypotension	2 (8.33%)	7 (29.16%)	0.0128
Bradycardia	1 (4.16%)	4 (16.66%)	0.0892

Discussion

Majority participants were between 31-40 years (45.83% in group A & 54.16% in group B) of age followed by 41-50 and 21-30 years. Mean BMI was 23.56 Kg/m² in group A and 24.28 Kg/m² in group B. Majority cases were

under ASA grade I (54.16 in group A & 62.5% in group B) in both study groups (Table 1).

The mean duration of onset and duration of peak of sensory block was 7.84 min and 11.03 min in isobaric levobupivacaine group and 5.54 min and 7.82 min in hyperbaric bupivacaine groups, respectively. The total duration of sensory block was 181.95 min in isobaric levobupivacaine group and 209.36 min in hyperbaric bupivacaine group. The mean duration of complete motor block was 8.81 min and 6.42 min, total duration of motor block was 205.34 min and 213.98 min and duration of analgesia was 130.48 min and 151.14 min in isobaric levobupivacaine group and in hyperbaric bupivacaine groups respectively. The mean difference of sensory block, motor block and total duration of analgesia between study groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). (Table 2).

Parashar *et al.*, found mean onset of sensory block at shin if tibia was 1.19 min and 1.10 min, at L1 level was 7.83 min and 3.07 min and at T10 level was 12.68 min and 7.22 min, maximum sensory level achieved was 23.03 min and 19.54 min and total duration of sensory block was 211.10 min and 193.13 min in isobaric bupivacaine and hyperbaric bupivacaine, respectively. The total duration of motor block was 198.76 min and 182.6 min in both study groups. The mean levels of sensory and motor blockade were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) [11]. Sujatha *et al.*, on comparison of intrathecal isobaric bupivacaine and isobaric levobupivacaine reported that mean onset of sensory (6.84 min and 5.64 min) and motor block (10.27 min and 9.28 min) and duration of sensory (207.8 min and 187.1 min) and motor block (240.21 min and 194.3 min) in bupivacaine and levobupivacaine groups respectively [12].

Singh *et al.*, reported no significant difference in terms of duration of sensory and motor blockade in levobupivacaine and bupivacaine groups, respectively [13]. Naithani *et al.*, reported mean duration of sensory and motor blockade was 188 min and 205 min in isobaric bupivacaine group and

217 min and 216 min in hyperbaric levobupivacaine group [14]. The present study findings were similar inline of above findings where mean duration of sensory and motor block was high in hyperbaric bupivacaine than isobaric levobupivacaine.

The mean systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure was comparatively low in hyperbaric bupivacaine group than isobaric levobupivacaine group. The mean difference of SBP was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Parashar *et al.*, reported that the fall of SBP (124.86 ± 4.6 mmHg to 118 ± 4.6 mmHg in group L and 123.8 ± 4.6 mmHg to 108.66 ± 1.8 mmHg in group B) and DBP (78.06 ± 4.6 mmHg to 69.5 ± 1.6 mmHg in group L and 79.6 ± 4.0 mmHg to 68 ± 1.6 mmHg in group B) was observed from baseline.

The mean difference was statistically significant after 5 min till end in SBP and from 15 min to 120 min in DBP [11] Singh *et al.*, reported that mean SBP was 121.35 mm of Hg and 124.26 mm of Hg at 30 min and 119.73 mm of Hg and 122.73 mm of Hg in bupivacaine and levobupivacaine groups respectively. The mean DBP was 80.52 mm of Hg and 81.56 mm of Hg at 30 min and 82.63 mm of Hg and 81.36 mm of Hg at 60 min in bupivacaine and levobupivacaine groups respectively. The mean difference of SBP and DBP was statistically not significant ($p > 0.05$) [13]. The findings of present study were consistent with above studies where SBP was reduced from 125.36 to 123.66 mm of Hg.

The mean pulse rate and mean arterial pressure was high in hyperbaric bupivacaine group than isobaric levobupivacaine group. The difference of mean pulse rate was statistically significant between two study groups ($p < 0.05$). Parashar *et al.*, reported that the fall of MAP was seen from 5 min till the end and the mean difference was statistically significant from 5 min to 150 min ($p < 0.05$)

[11]. Singh *et al.*, reported that the mean MAP was 94.01 mm of Hg and 96.52 mm of Hg at 30 min and 94.99 mm of Hg and 95.05 mm of Hg at 60 min in bupivacaine and levobupivacaine groups respectively with no significant difference among two groups ($p>0.05$) [13]. The mean SPO₂ was comparable between two study groups. However, the mean difference of SPO₂ was statistically not significant between study groups ($p>0.05$) (Graph 5). Singh *et al.*, reported that the mean SPO₂ was comparable between two study group, but the difference was statistically not significant ($p>0.05$) [3].

Hypotension was seen in 7 cases, nausea in 5 cases and bradycardia in 4 cases of hyperbaric bupivacaine group. However, in isobaric levobupivacaine group nausea and hypotension was seen in two cases and bradycardia in one case (Table 3). Sujatha *et al.*, reported that hypotension (50%), bradycardia (35%) and nausea (12.5%) are commonly encountered in bupivacaine group. Whereas in levobupivacaine group hypotension and bradycardia was seen in 20% and 10% of cases [12] Singh *et al.*, reported that incidence of hypotension was 36.6% and 16.6% in bupivacaine and levobupivacaine groups respectively [13].

Parashar *et al.*, concluded that intrathecal administration of 3ml of 0.5% isobaric bupivacaine was safer alternative in spinal anaesthesia than 3ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine [1]. Dinesh *et al.*, reported that 15mg intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine is rapid in onset, prolonged and higher level of sensory block, prolonged motor blockade compared to ropivacaine in lower limb surgeries [11] Sujatha *et al.*, concluded that intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine was less cardiotoxic, neurotoxic and effective local anaesthetic agent compared to isobaric bupivacaine [12] Singh *et al.*, concluded that bupivacaine and levobupivacaine are effective drugs, however, bupivacaine group showed earlier onset of action [13].

Naithani *et al.*, stated that isobaric levobupivacaine is effective in sensory and motor blockade and maintain stable hemodynamic parameters than hyperbaric bupivacaine [14]. Ramya *et al.*, on comparison of isobaric levobupivacaine with hyperbaric bupivacaine in spinal anaesthesia undergoing lower abdominal surgeries concluded that isobaric levobupivacaine is an effective drug, providing an effective sensory motor blockade with stable haemodynamic profile and decreased CNS and CVS toxicity than hyperbaric bupivacaine [15].

Samar *et al.*, reported that isobaric levobupivacaine was effective in early onset of sensory and motor block and prolonged duration of sensory and motor block and stable haemodynamic parameters than isobaric ropivacaine in lower limb surgeries [16].

Hoda *et al.*, reported that isobaric levobupivacaine was safe and effective and choice for spinal anaesthesia in cases undergoing prolonged lower abdominal surgeries [17].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine has less duration slow onset of sensory and motor blockade and incidence of hypotension, bradycardia and nausea was less than intrathecal hyperbaric bupivacaine.

References

1. Mazy, A., Ghanem, M.A., Abd Elatif, M.S.E. *et al.* Spinal anaesthesia for lengthy lower limb orthopaedic surgeries: dexmedetomidine plus fentanyl versus dexmedetomidine. *Ain-Shams J Anesthesiol.* 2019;11(10):1-8.
2. Hodgson PS, Neal JM, Pollock JE, Liu SS. The neurotoxicity of drugs given intrathecally (spinal) *Anesth Analg.* 1999; 88:797–809.
3. Barash PG, Cullen BF, Stoelting RK, editors. Philadelphia: Lippincott

- Williams and Wilkins; Clinical Anaesthesia. 2001;451-66.
4. Polley LS, Columb MO, Naughton NN, Wagner DS, van de ven CJM. Relative analgesic potencies of ropivacaine and bupivacaine for epidural analgesia in labor. *Anaesthesiology*. 1999; 90:944-50.
 5. Lyons G, Columb M, Wilson RC, Johnson RV. Epidural pain relief in labour: potencies of levobupivacaine and racemic bupivacaine. *Br J Anaesth*. 1998; 81:899-901.
 6. Breebaart MB, Vercauteren MP, Hoffmann VL, Adriaensen HA. Urinary bladder scanning after day-case arthroscopy under spinal anaesthesia: Comparison between lidocaine, ropivacaine, and levobupivacaine. *Br J Anaesth*. 2003; 90:309-13.
 7. Solakovic N. Comparison of Hemodynamic Effects of Hyperbaric and Isobaric Bupivacaine in Spinal Anaesthesia. *Med Arh* 2010; 64(1):11-14.
 8. Fettes PDW, Hocking G, Peterson MK, Luck JF and Wildsmith JAW. Comparison of plain and hyperbaric solutions of ropivacaine for spinal anaesthesia. *Br J Anaesth*. 2005; 94(1): 107-11.
 9. Gori F, Corradetti F, Cerotto V, Peduto VA. Influence of positioning on plain levobupivacaine spinal anesthesia in cesarean section. *Anesthesiol Res Pract*. 2010; 2010:212696.
 10. Glaser C, Marhofer P, Zimpfer G, Heinz MT, Sitzwohl C, Kapral S. Levobupivacaine versus racemic bupivacaine for spinal anesthesia. *Anesth Analg*. 2002; 94:194-8.
 11. Parashar P, Singh A, Sharma MK, Raval DL. Comparison between isobaric levobupivacaine 0.5% and hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5% in spinal anesthesia in lower limb surgeries and lower abdominal surgeries in adult patients. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2021; 9:418-22.
 12. Sujatha C, Chandraleela S, Arthi A. Comparative evaluation of anesthetic efficacy and hemodynamic effects of intrathecal isobaric bupivacaine versus intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine in the lower abdominal and lower limb surgeries. *Asian Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2022;13(9):57-62.
 13. Singh AK, Selvakumar P, Selvaraju K. To evaluate efficacy and safety of isobaric levobupivacaine versus hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb orthopaedic surgeries. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*. 2022; 09(03):310-316.
 14. Naithani U, Malleshappa K, Madhanmohan *et al*. Comparison of intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine with hyperbaric bupivacaine in spinal anesthesia for lower limb orthopedic surgeries. *Int J Health Sci Res*. 2015; 5(10):73-84.
 15. Ramya M, Kalyan CP, Hemnath BK, Jyotsna RP, Arun P. Comparison of Isobaric Levobupivacaine with Hyperbaric Bupivacaine in spinal anaesthesia in patients undergoing Lower Abdominal Surgeries. *JMSCR*. 2019; 07(12): 731-737.
 16. Samar P, Pandya S, Dhawale TA. Intrathecal Use of Isobaric Levobupivacaine 0.5% Versus Isobaric Ropivacaine 0.75% for Lower Abdominal and Lower Limb Surgeries. *Cureus*. 2020 May 31;12(5): e8373.
 17. Hoda W, Kumar A, Roychoudhury P. Isobaric levobupivacaine a better and safer substitute for spinal anaesthesia in patients undergoing prolonged lower abdominal and lower limb surgeries. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2018; 6:3111-5.